

C4 Model: A Research Guide for Designing Software Architectures

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Abstract—Given nowadays increasing complexity of software systems, their architectural design prior to their actual implementation becomes quite complicated. As a result, robust architectural design methodologies need to be put in place to ensure systems’ interoperability, maintainability, as well as performance. This work explores the significance of having in place a Software Architecture (SA) for these systems, emphasizing on the underlying architecture design and modeling principles. Among the various existing architectural design approaches, the C4 model has gained prominence for its clarity and hierarchical representation of systems’ components, being furtherly investigated in this work. To this context, the advantages of adopting the C4 model in SA design is presented, detailing its four-layered structure (i.e., Context, Container, Component, Code). To depict the documented concepts into a real case study, the C4 model is exploited for illustrating the FAME Data Marketplace’s architecture, summarizing the contributing remarks of such model upon the FAME system. The study highlights how the C4 model enhances communication among stakeholders, facilitates system maintenance, and improves overall software design, while the future work includes extending this modeling approach to additional real-world case studies.

Keywords—Software, Architecture Design, Architecture Modeling, Viewpoints, C4 Model, FAME, Data Marketplace

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for vital, reliable, diverse, and decentralised systems has grown in the software sector. Systems’ architectures, on the one hand, are acknowledged as the foundation of any software system and are essential to guaranteeing its quality, including interoperability, performance, portability, adaptability, and maintainability [1], [2]. Either speaking about Software Architecture (SA) or Reference Architecture (RA) [3], both have become a generally accepted concept in research and industry. Large and increasingly dynamic software systems can now be designed, developed, and evolved with greater control thanks to the widely acknowledged significance of stressing the system’s components and their connectors.

According to one of the classic architecture books [4], software architects must address the fundamental elements of (i) breaking down the problem into manageable chunks in order to comprehend it as a whole, and (ii) elucidating the architecture’s purpose, operation, and rationale, as well as the decisions that were made to arrive at this final outcome, while simultaneously utilising abstractions to precisely define each of these concepts. In essence, software architects have to provide additional justification for the software’s design choices by demonstrating how the requirements and the built system align. By providing a clear design, they can guarantee to all the involved parties that the system will meet all the functional and quality requirements, aiding them to efficiently understand the goals of the system.

To successfully perform such task, software architects have to properly design and model the system’s SA, helping all the parties to cohesively work together as the relevant system is developed and evolve [5]. Such design is a concrete artifact that provides pertinent details about the system and is frequently employed in the assessment of various designs [6]. According to the current research [7], it is evident that SA descriptions come in a variety of formats and contain a variety of aspects, which can be occasionally misunderstood and, consequently, make the use or distribution of these designs challenging. Hence, given the available alternatives for designing SAs [8], software architects must make a difficult decision for the methodologies to use to better describe the architecture of their systems.

To this context, there exist three (3) general approaches for modeling a SA (i.e., informal, semi-formal, fully-formal) [7], with the fully-formal ones being the most preferable, focusing especially on the viewpoints approach [7]. In this approach, diagrams are grouped according to the viewpoint of the SA they depict, with a subset of these systems attempting to divide the diagrams according to the stakeholder demands. Even though in the literature there have been proposed thousands of different ways for representing a system’s SA through the viewpoints approach, the most widely used ones include the models of ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2022 [9], V&B [10], RM-ODP [11], S4V [12], BAPO/CAFCR [13], Kruchten 4+1 [14], and C4 [15], all

of them having as a common goal to empower stakeholders to examine system designs in a methodical and simplified manner.

Considering all these aspects and existing research, this study primarily focuses on the investigation of the C4 model viewpoints approach, trying to identify and provide the reasons for adopting such model when designing a SA, while at the same time providing a research-oriented methodology on how this modeling approach can be successfully put into practice step-by-step, presenting a real use case scenario of a complex system that has modeled its SA based on the C4 model. The latter refers to the FAME Data Marketplace [16], which has been built as a functional platform to federate data and technology assets for Embedded Finance (EmFi) data-driven applications in compliance with the EU data strategy and regulations. More detail of FAME's underlying system is provided in Section IV.

The rest of this work is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of the basic concepts to be considered when designing and modeling a SA. Section III provides the essentials for understanding and effectively exploiting the C4 model towards modeling complete and easily understandable system's SA. Section IV delivers information for the FAME Data Marketplace that is used as a real world example exploiting the C4 model upon its SA, whilst Section V concludes this work, explaining the gained insights, as well as our future plans.

II. BACKGROUND CONCEPTS

A. Software Architecture

It is generally known that every system has an architecture [17]. The so called Software Architecture (SA) of a system is *“the structure or structures of the system, which comprise software elements, the externally visible properties of those elements, and the relationships among them”* [18]. While this definition provides the structural aspects of SA, the IEEE 2000 standard definition [19] emphasizes on other aspects of SA: *“Architecture is the fundamental organization of a system embodied in its components, their relationships to each other and to the environment and the principles guiding its design and evolution”*. This definition stresses that a system's SA is not only the system's model at a certain point in time, but it also includes principles that guide its design and evolution. Essentially, via SAs software architects seek to demonstrate that creating a SA involves choosing which components and interaction patterns to employ and what limitations are placed on those patterns.

One unique kind of architecture that offers important guidance for the development of concrete architectures of a certain class of systems is Reference Architecture (RA) [20]. In essence, RAs aggregate information about how to construct systems' SAs of a specific application domain, referring to an architecture at a higher degree of abstraction than the concrete systems' architectures (i.e., SAs). It primarily covers software components, architectural styles and patterns, standards and laws, domain business rules, and best practices for software development in that field. Therefore, RAs' fundamental function is to act as a roadmap for the creation, standardisation, and advancement of systems [21][22][23].

Based on these, the correlation and differentiation between RAs and SAs is quite clear. RAs aim to provide a common vocabulary, reusable designs, and best practices that are used as

a guidance for more concrete SAs in a specific domain. It acts as a “reference” for the particular architectures that stakeholders will use to address their own problems, never meant to be implemented as-is. On the contrary, it should be utilized as a benchmark to start for the architectural efforts of different organizations. Thus, a RA can serve as a template that can be used to create a specific architecture for a software (i.e., SA). However, either speaking for RAs or SAs, the same approaches can be utilized to design and model the underlying architecture, including either informal, or semi-formal, or fully-formal modeling methods. Though, it is worth mentioning that RAs are considered by a part of the research community as very distant from SAs in the sense that RAs are not architectures, but instead are useful concepts that capture elements of an architecture [18].

B. Software Architecture Design

An architectural description can include information regarding both RAs and SAs. The latter is more valuable when specified and used before system development, but it can also be effectively used after a system has been established (e.g., for system maintenance). Its basic scope is to help its stakeholders to have conversations about the system that will be constructed [24]. Stakeholders may be sure they have reached a consensus on the features and design decisions they would anticipate, being included in the system by deciding on a SA in advance.

However, explaining a system's architecture is frequently an intensive procedure that calls for patience, tool expertise, as well as documentation and diagramming skills. In actuality, avoiding two (2) concrete situations is the largest problem in SA design and documentation: (i) The complexity of the architectural documentation, which most of the times tends to become confused and obsolete, losing its purpose, and (ii) The “poorness” of the documentation, which may contain limited or incorrect information. Consequently, implementing systems' architectural design and description becomes of utmost importance for building effective and complete systems.

Even though it is a common consensus that there exist three (3) general approaches for designing and documenting a SA (i.e., informal, semi-formal, fully-formal descriptions), the current work has been based on the fact that nowadays there is a great need on investigating and adopting the fully-formal methods, primarily focusing on the viewpoints' modeling approach. Such methods are widely adopted since they are breaking up the description of a system into separate perspectives (i.e., viewpoints) that address the diverse concerns that stakeholders have with the system. In turn, these viewpoints are containing multiple diagrams to describe the complete system. Hence, a viewpoint model defines the relevant aspects or concerns that must be taken care of when designing a SA.

Numerous case studies and theories grounded in real-world experience have been published in this field, confirming the necessity of multiple architectural views to capture different perspectives of a SA [24]. All these studies make clear that the effectiveness of having multiple architectural views is that they can aid developers to better manage the complexity of the underlying systems by separating their different aspects into separate views [25]. It is important to note though, that the concept of architectural views is not entirely new, having scholarly roots in the work of David Parnas from 1970 and more

recently in the work of Dewayne Perry and Alex Wolf from 1990 [26]. The mid-1990s saw the beginning of a general understanding of viewpoints, and since then, several collections of viewpoints have been formed. Some of these solutions are currently at their early stage, whereas some others have gained popularity in practice over the years [27].

One of these solutions refers to the C4 model [28], which has gained a lot of popularity during the recent years, having been proposed to aid software architects to solve the problem of documenting faulty architectures that are hard to be understood and maintained. In essence, the C4 model provides a hierarchical set of diagrams to describe SA at different levels of abstraction, which allow software architects to express different stories to different audiences. Thus, these diagrams provide a clear and concise representation of a SA, making it easy to be understood by any involved stakeholder (whether referring to developers, business people, or clients). All these constitute the reason why this work primarily examines this model, since to the best of our knowledge, currently, a stepwise research methodology and real-world evaluation cases of this model are limited.

III. C4 MODEL ESSENTIALS

A. C4 Model Overview

Various engineers frequently use their own specialized notations to model and validate systems utilizing low-fidelity software models and fragmented architectural specifications. Since these models are usually not updated or documented over the course of the system’s lifecycle, it is challenging to forecast how any new modifications will affect the system, potentially compromising its overall functionality. The unexpected effects of the applied design approaches or changes are discovered only late in the lifecycle when they are much more expensive to be resolved. An approach to avoid this situation and effectively design, develop, and maintain a SA is model-based SA, through which software development teams can: (i) lower risk via early and repeated SA analysis, (ii) lower cost via fewer issues with system integration and simplified lifecycle support, (iii) evaluate effects of architectural decisions, and (iv) boost confidence by validating modelling assumptions in the operational system.

In order to assist software development teams in describing and communicating their SA, both during upfront design meetings and while retrospectively documenting an existing codebase, the C4 model was developed. Through this model, software development teams can efficiently create maps of their code at various levels of detail [28]. C4 is essentially an abstraction-first method for SA diagramming, built on abstractions that represent the way software development teams conceptualize and construct their systems.

In short, Simon Brown constructed the C4 model based on the 4+1 architectural perspective model [14] and UML [29]. This model breaks down the software into smaller units, distinguishing the diagram levels to system’s Context, Container, Component, and Code, which actually represent the “C4” name of the model. Like the agile methodology, the C4 model is suggested when quick and efficient sharing and constant updates of a software architecture during ongoing software development are required.

B. C4 Model Baseline Concepts

To describe a SA, the C4 model indicates two (2) basic concepts: (i) abstractions to describe the architecture, and (ii) diagrams to visualize the abstractions. In detail, the four (4) supported diagram levels (i.e., Context, Container, Component, Code) act as the visual map of the underlying system with defined abstractions’ levels. These are made for various audiences, from developers (low level diagrams) to non-technical consumers (high level diagrams) [30]. An easy-to-understand illustration of this is Google Maps, where users may zoom in to reduce or enlarge the architectural design. Similarly, the C4 model has Context, Container, Component, and Code, just as a map has Continent, Country, State, and City. A summarization of the model’s abstractions is given in Table I.

TABLE I. C4 MODEL ABSTRACTIONS

<i>Abstraction</i>	<i>Description</i>
Person	Any end-user who uses the system
System	The highest level of abstraction representing the existing/under development systems, and their interactions
Container	Any application, datastore, service, etc. that makes up the system (being independently deployable and runnable)
Component	Any building block and module that makes up each container of the system (not being deployed independently)
Relation	Any dependency/data flow between the other Abstractions

As for the four (4) supported diagram types, as they represent the visual representations of how a system works (exploiting the abovementioned abstractions), they are split up into the levels depicted in Table II. More specifically, Table II provides additional detail for each diagram regarding the purpose, abstractions, and audience on which each diagram refers to.

TABLE II. C4 MODEL DIAGRAM TYPES

<i>Diagram</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Abstraction</i>	<i>Audience</i>
Level 1 - Context	High-level view of built system, depicting how it interacts with external people and systems	Person, System	Everybody (Software architects, Business people, etc.)
Level 2 - Container	Zoomed-in view of built system, showing the containers being executed inside it	Person, System, Container	Software architects, Developers, Support staff
Level 3 - Component	Zoomed-in view of each container, depicting all the components making it up, their tasks and their implementation detail	System, Container, Component	Software architects, Developers
Level 4 - Code (optional)	UML diagrams of each component, zooming into component’s implementation detail – also autogenerated from source code	Component	Software architects, Developers

It should be noted that additional diagrams can be created to cover further information such as deployment details, event sequence, and higher-level system interactions [31]. Fig. 1 shows a summary of the C4 core diagrams and their correlations, where a system can be composed of one or more containers (datastores, services, etc.), each of which may contain one or

more components, which in turn can be implemented by one or more code elements (objects, functions, classes, etc.).

Fig. 1. C4 Model Diagram Types.

Lastly, it should be noted that one of the advantages of the C4 model is that it consistently uses explicit descriptions for each diagram, avoiding the ambiguity that UML may cause with its complex syntax. Rather than standardizing a syntax, the C4 notation focusses more on creating understandable diagrams and breaking the system down into its four (4) levels, not mandating strict rules for its notation. As long as it is clearly described, there are no limitations on modifying any elements or notations to fit the application domain of the target system.

C. C4 Model Design Process

To ensure software architects that they are correctly adopting and putting into practice the C4 model design approach, some concrete steps should be followed for each designed diagram. For better interpreting the underlying process, an easy-to-follow example is provided upon an eMarket system.

To begin with, when drafting the *Context* diagram, software architects must show all the built system's interactions in a macro way, without much detail, concentrating on how users and external systems interact with the built system. At this level, the diagram should be technology agnostic, focusing on the people and software systems instead of low-level detail. To complete such procedure, the following steps must be applied:

Step 1: Create the target system box/description (e.g., eMarket).

Fig. 2. Context diagram [Target system].

Step 2: Add a box with a description for each external system (e.g., Payment Service) and user (e.g., Customer) involved in the target system. These systems/users shall be differentiated in the diagram, shown with diverse colours or icons.

Fig. 3. Context diagram [External systems and users].

Step 3: Draw annotated lines to show the elements' interactions.

Fig. 4. Context diagram [Target system's interactions – Step 1].

Step 4: Repeat Step 2 – Step 3 until having in the diagram all the involved external systems and users, ultimately providing a broad overview of the architecture of the entire system.

Fig. 5. Context diagram [Target system's interactions – Step 2].

In sequel, the *Container* diagram should be drafted, where software architects must illustrate the target system in more detail, describing the containers (e.g., web application, database) that it will offer and how these will interact. At this level, emphasis must be on the functional description, making clear each container's technologies. The involved steps refer to:

Step 1: Draw the boundaries of the target system (e.g., eMarket), and add the external systems' boxes (e.g., Payment/Email Service, Shipment) and users (e.g., Customer, Admin) being related to the target system (coming from the *Context* diagram).

Fig. 6. Container diagram [Boundaries of target system].

Step 2: List up and add in the form of boxes the software elements that can be independently deployed in the form of a container (e.g., Web/Mobile Application, eMarket Middleware, Database) within the target system, and then use lines with the appropriate annotation to show the relationships between each container and the users and external systems. Emphasize which technology is used in each element by adding this information either in the boxes' descriptions or in the lines of the relations.

Fig. 7. Container diagram [Target system containers].

Then, the *Component* diagram should be built, where software architects must depict all the parts that make up each container of the previous diagram (i.e., *Container*). At this level, more information regarding the roles, interactions and technology shall appear, following the steps of:

Step 1: Draw the boundaries of the target container (e.g., eMarket Middleware), and add the component elements' boxes related to the target container (from the *Container* diagram).

Fig. 8. Component diagram [Boundaries of a container].

Step 2: List up and add in the form of boxes the functional modules (i.e., components) of the target container (e.g., eMarket Middleware), and draw the needed lines to elaborate on their roles and their relations with the relevant technologies and implementation. Ideally, the technology or protocol used for data exchange should be included in the lines for the connected components, giving further detail upon the *Container* diagram.

Fig. 9. Component diagram [Container components].

Step 3: Repeat Step 2 until all the containers of the target system have their own *Component* diagram. Hence, the target system will likely end up having more than one *Component* diagram.

Finally, the *Code* diagram could be specified through UML diagrams [29], such as class, sequence, component diagrams, etc., aiding software architects to represent the very specific implementation of each component illustrated in the *Component* diagrams. Though, *Code* diagrams can be fully skipped, since they are not recommended to be drawn unless the underlying component is very important or complicated.

When drafting all these diagrams, software architects should not forget to: (i) keep the diagrams simple and avoid excessive detail, (ii) provide consistent notation among all the diagrams, (iii) give a title to each diagram, indicating its level, (iv) be wary of using initials or acronyms, (v) be explicit for the type of all the depicted elements, (vi) add a mini description to all the depicted elements, and (vii) favour uni-directional lines, adding a short description to all the drawn lines.

D. C4 Model Designing Tools

Rather than begin drafting all these C4 model diagrams from scratch, software architects can use existing tools that support the easy and smooth creation of these diagrams. By exploiting such tools, they can document their SA in a way that is easy to be understood by all the stakeholders, ensuring at the same time the successful system's development and maintenance. To this context, there exists various tools supporting the creation of C4 model diagrams, either being "drag and drop" (e.g., Icepanel [32], Diagrams.net [33], Visual Paradigm [34], Lucidchart [35]) or "text-based" (e.g., C4-Builder [36], Structurizr [37], CodeSee [38], Mermaid [39], C4-PlantUML [40]).

What is worth mentioning as a powerful feature of most of these tools is their collaboration capabilities. In particular, they allow multiple users to work simultaneously on the same C4 diagram, aiding teamwork and cooperation that is quite useful in a team setting, where several people may need to contribute to a SA. Also, they allow software architects to share their diagrams with other team members, making it easy to get feedback/input from them. This can lead to a more robust and well-rounded SA, as diverse perspectives can provide valuable insights.

IV. C4 MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

A. FAME Overview

To put into practice the C4 model and apply all the baseline concepts and design practices introduced by this model, this work exploits the system of the FAME Data Marketplace [16], for effectively designing its SA. More precisely, FAME aims to create, implement, and launch a distinctive, reliable, secure, and energy-efficient Federated Data Space for the EmFi application domain [41]. The core system of FAME is a Data Marketplace that heavily relies on its developed Federated Data Assets Catalogue (FDAC) where all of the system's data assets are indexed, and then can be securely shared, monetized and traded. To achieve this, FAME offers novel features in three (3) areas: (i) trading and pricing of decentralised and programmable data assets using blockchain tokenisation techniques, (ii) safe, interoperable, and regulatory-compliant data exchange across multiple federated data providers in-line with EU initiatives, and (iii) integrating trusted and energy-efficient analytics based on cutting-edge technologies like explainable artificial intelligence (XAI), situation aware explainability (SAX), and incremental energy-efficient and power-efficient edge analytics [42].

To successfully put all these concepts and technologies into place, the FAME SA has been produced, consisting of a core software system that is divided into five (5) layers, namely the: (i) Dashboard, (ii) Open APIs, (iii) Federation Manager, (iv) Transactional Operations, and (v) Energy Efficient Analytics Services. In short, the core software system namely FAME Federated Data Marketplace, acts as a global data marketplace that can be accessible by any external stakeholder coming from diverse domains (i.e., business, citizens, research and academia, local, national, European governments, and public bodies). All these parties can either contribute their own data assets (e.g., datasets, analytical models, software), or access the FAME’s existing ones, also being able to access FAME functionalities via open APIs. All of this is made feasible by providing the stakeholders with an easy-to-use dashboard that serves as a single-entry point for all the integrated data assets, allowing the stakeholders to find, access, monetise, price, and trade their assets. All these assets are located in one centralised location, the FDAC, which consists of both semantically annotated assets and direct links to non-annotated assets of the underlying data sources. The FDAC provides a variety of APIs for asset’s access, search, and query, guaranteeing a smooth and platform-neutral experience for FAME’s end users. Additional detail for all these features are provided in the rest of this Section.

B. FAME Software Architecture through C4 Model

By the early stages of its SA design and modeling, FAME has adopted the C4 model for covering such purposes, since its main goal was to have a clear vision of what kind of system is needed to be built (both at a technical and at a business level), contributing to the evolution of the system and the creation of a solid roadmap. By using the C4, this goal was achieved in an agile manner, enhancing the project as a whole. Additionally, this model allowed the FAME consortium to share the project’s architectural knowledge with the community in a simplified manner, with a clear goal and a high value. To this context, FAME has followed all the C4 guidelines (Section III) for its SA, applying in its diagrams (Context, Container, Component) the notations of Table III, Table IV, Table V respectively.

TABLE III. FAME SA CONTEXT DIAGRAM NOTATIONS

<i>Abstraction</i>	<i>FAME Notation</i>	<i>Notation Description</i>
Person [Data Provider]		Any end-user that provides data assets to FAME.
Person [Data Consumer]		Any end-user that consumes data assets from FAME.
Person [FAME Admin]		Any administrator that has access to the admin functionalities of FAME.
System [Target]		The system that is built within FAME.
System [External]		Any external system interacting with FAME.
Relationship		Any relationship between abstractions.

TABLE IV. FAME SA CONTAINER DIAGRAM NOTATIONS

<i>Abstraction</i>	<i>FAME Notation</i>	<i>Notation Description</i>
Person [Data Provider]		Any end-user that provides data assets to FAME.
Person [Data Consumer]		Any end-user that consumes data assets from FAME.
Person [FAME Admin]		Any administrator that has access to the admin functionalities of FAME.
System [External]		Any external system interacting with FAME.
Container [Any type]		Any container executed inside the system of FAME.
Container [Database]		Any database lying within the system of FAME.
Container [Web Browser]		Any web browser (or UI) exploited inside the depicted system of FAME.
Relationship		Any relationship between abstractions.

TABLE V. FAME SA COMPONENT DIAGRAM NOTATIONS

<i>Abstraction</i>	<i>FAME Notation</i>	<i>Notation Description</i>
Component		Any component executed inside the depicted container.
Container [Any type]		Any container interacting with the depicted container.
Container [Database]		Any database exploited inside the depicted container.
Container [Web Browser]		Any web browser (or UI) lying within the depicted container.
System [External]		Any external system interacting with the depicted container.
Relationship		Any relationship between abstractions.

Additional detail follow along with the FAME C4 model of Level 1 (*Context*), Level 2 (*Container*), Level 3 (*Component*) diagrams, describing the overall flow of the FAME system, the interactions among its containers and components, as well as the added-value for all of its interacting stakeholders (end-users). Level 4 (*Code*) diagram has not been produced, since such level of detail was not required for the system’s SA. To this end, it should be noted that the purpose of this Section is not to describe in deep detail the FAME SA, but rather describe the idea of how FAME SA has been produced exploiting the C4 model.

To begin with, Fig. 10 illustrates the *Context* diagram of the FAME SA, depicting the target system (i.e., FAME Federated Data Marketplace) and the diverse groups of stakeholders that are able to interact with it (i.e., Data Provider, Data Consumer, FAME Administrator), highlighting the means of how they can achieve this interaction. In parallel, all the interacting external

systems are depicted, referring to any external Data Marketplace or Data Space that intends to share its data assets with the FAME Federated Data Marketplace. A description has been added to all the illustrated abstractions, whilst detailed explanations have been provided upon all the captured relationships. To this end, it should be mentioned that the notations in Fig. 10 refer to the ones described in Table III, whereas to construct this diagram all the guidelines provided in Section III applied step-by-step.

Fig. 10. FAME SA C4 context diagram.

Diving deeper into the *Container* diagram of the FAME SA, a zoomed-in view of the built system is provided in Fig. 11, showing the containers executed inside its system. To better reflect and group the overall system’s functionalities and inner containers, the latter have been grouped into the five (5) layers of Dashboard, Open APIs, Federation Manager, Transactional Operations, and Energy Efficient Analytics Services, highlighted within the discrete light-blue boxes. As in the case of the previous diagram, detailed explanations have been added to all the captured abstractions and relationships, applying the notations of Table IV and the guidelines provided in Section III.

In brief, the *Dashboard* layer provides all the means for providing access to all the FAME stakeholders to the supported functionalities of the FAME Federated Data Marketplace. Thus, this layer includes the containers of: (i) Stakeholders UI that acts as a user-friendly and easy-to-use UI for direct access to all the underlying FAME functionalities, (ii) Helpdesk that aids stakeholders to report and resolve any operational or technical identified issues, (iii) Learning Centre that provides a pool of training assets’ resources, notably resources related with EmFi applications, boosting the platform’s usability and adoption, (iv) Regulatory Compliance for providing legal support upon the relevant applicable laws and the regulations of the assets to be indexed (e.g., GDPR, MiFiD, EU AI Act), and (v) Administrator UI for allowing the FAME administrator to access the system for administration purposes. As for the *Open APIs* layer, it acts as an additional interacting point with the FAME system, allowing stakeholders to have direct access to the selected underlying operations. To this context, it includes the containers of: (i) APIs Execution that allows stakeholders to exploit the existing open functionalities of the platform, and (ii) API Documentation that provides a proper documentation for describing each API along with tutorials and exploitation guidelines. Regarding the *Federation Manager* layer, it contains all the methods and techniques for realizing the federated functionalities of FAME, offering the containers of the: (i) Authentication & Authorization through which any external stakeholder or the FAME administrator can be authenticated and granted access to the platform, (ii) Assets Policy Management for producing the relevant policy rules of any asset to be indexed into the marketplace, (iii) Semantic Interoperability that transforms the assets’ data from its source formats and semantics to the FAME ontologies to provide an interoperable view of all the assets included into the marketplace, (iv) Semantic Search Engine that offers the functionality of semantically searching the assets lying in the marketplace, and (v) FDAC that keeps the information of all the system’s data assets. In sequel, the

Fig. 11. FAME SA C4 container diagram

Transactional Operations layer contains the capabilities that are mostly related to the daily operation of a Data Marketplace that supports trading, including the containers of the: (i) Assets Provenance & Tracing that supports the FDAC by extending the metadata model of the data assets to be indexed or traded within FAME with additional attributes, (ii) Assets Pricing that can be exploited by the data providers of any asset to be indexed or traded within FAME with additional attributes, (iii) Assets Trading & Monetization for managing the data assets' trading schemes as well as the assets' produced offering details, and (iv) Operational Governance for onboarding of the end-users, storing the offerings (extending the FDAC metadata model), managing the subscriptions, and supporting auxiliary functions like billing. Finally, the *Energy Efficient Analytics Services* layer offers the necessary tools for implementing analytical functionalities (being provided as assets through FAME) for EmFi applications, including the containers of the: (i) AI & ML Analytics that provides a library of state-of-the-art AI/ML models that can be applied either to existing or to newly indexed data assets to transform, reform, and derive data-driven insights as new tradeable assets within FAME, (ii) SAX & XAI Techniques that can be applied upon the produced AI/ML models to ensure models' trustworthiness, (iii) CO₂ Monitoring that can be also applied upon the produced AI/ML models to capture their CPU/GPU usage and emitted CO₂ footprint, (iv) Smart Deployment that exploits the above metrics to provide deployment configurations that optimize the models' CO₂ emissions, (v) Incremental & Energy Efficient (EE) Analytics that supports the execution of the AI & ML Analytics in the cases where an external Big Data source is integrated within FAME for providing its data, and (vi) Federated Machine Learning (FML) Orchestrator, Server and Client provide a FML infrastructure for the scenarios where FAME stakeholders have their data distributed across different databases (silos), or where they want to leverage collaboration between companies to extract insights from their data in a federated manner.

Moving into the next diagram level (*Component diagram*), since the overall platform includes twenty-two (22) diverse containers (as depicted in Fig. 11) and it would be extensive to depict all of them in this work, Fig. 12 provides the *Component diagram* for one of the containers of the system namely "Assets Provenance & Tracing". As in the case of the rest of the diagrams, explanations have been added to all the captured abstractions and relationships, applying the notations of Table V and the guidelines provided in Section III. Briefly, the Assets Provenance & Tracing container provides the means for ensuring the quality of metadata published on the FDAC, being exploited by the data providers of the marketplace. This is achieved by storing on a blockchain the digital fingerprint of the assets' metadata, so that the integrity of any FDAC entry can be verified on a Tracing Ledger. The same blockchain also maintains a registry of authentic sources, the Provenance Ledger, which can be referenced in FDAC entries as the provenance of the underlying assets. A separate database, the Offering Catalogue, supports the FDAC, the Operational Governance and the Assets Trading & Monetization containers by linking the offering definitions (i.e., the formal description of the terms and conditions under which access to digital content is sold through FAME) to the assets published on the catalogue.

Fig. 12. FAME Assets Provenance & Tracing C4 component diagram.

C. C4 Model Contribution within FAME

Having analyzed the C4-oriented FAME SA within the FAME team members, presenting it at the same time in different events and external stakeholders' communities (both business and academic), it was revealed that having exploited the C4 model aid all the involved parties to better follow and interpret the system's scope and functionalities, more efficiently providing their feedback. More specifically, by exploiting the C4 model, FAME enhanced its efficiency in various directions:

(i) *Clear Communication*: Within FAME, the C4 model has enhanced the communication among all the team members by providing a common language for describing the SA of the built system, avoiding any misinterpretations. By adopting the models' clear graphical notation, all of the members were able to easily visualize the SA, thus a better understanding was promoted among all the team members and stakeholders. On top, when new team members were onboarded, it was easy to comprehend the SA using these diagrams.

(ii) *Improved Software Design*: Since the C4 model was put into place by the early stages of the FAME SA, it was easier for the members (especially the development teams) to detect potential design issues early in the development process, since the overall SA was broken down into three (3) diagram levels of different levels of detail. Thus, from the very beginning the members were able to gain a comprehensive understanding of the target system, contributing towards its successful final delivery.

(iii) *Complete Documentation*: By creating all the C4 model diagrams, proper documentation was produced during the release of the FAME SA, ensuring that all the SA aspects are covered via the provided diagrams. Hence, this documentation served as a valuable resource for the development teams and all the involved stakeholders, since all of them were able to easily understand the FAME SA baseline methods and techniques.

(iv) *Efficient System Maintenance and Evolution*: Like all the complex systems, the FAME system had also to deliver different versions of its SA to depict any identified technical issues, adapt to newly requirements, or enhance the existing information. To this context, by exploiting the C4 model, the FAME SA can be easily maintained given the clear view that is provided through the diagrams' layered representation, which make clear the intricate interconnections between all the system's components. When developers want to implement changes, this clarity is essential as it enables them to recognize any implications.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Given the demanding functionalities of current systems, SA is of utmost importance for designing, modeling and delivering such systems. The major impact behind this relies on the fact that SA (i) offers an overview that enables stakeholders' interaction at the beginning of the design process, (ii) allows for early assessment of quality attributes, and (iii) transfers the decisions captured in the SA to other systems. Creating a SA is often a laborious task that calls for patience, expertise, documenting and diagramming skills. Thus, proper decisions must be made by software architects when designing a system, applying a standardized way and best practices to provide such design. The viewpoints modeling approach has been proved to be widely adopted in various research studies, with C4 model being the one taking up space in the recent years. This work has studied the C4 model, offering a research-oriented methodology on how this design approach can be put into practice, applying it into the FAME real case study, to depict how the C4 model can benefit the SA modeling of complex systems. To enhance the findings, our future plans include the implementation of this model in existing scenarios of under development systems (i.e., [43][44][45][46]), and under research ones (i.e., [47][48][49]), which currently exploit informal design approaches. To verify the designing effectiveness of those SA via the C4 model, relevant questionnaires will be answered by stakeholders to gather feedback whether their SAs are better interpreted.

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